

Rhythmicalizer Revisited: Adapting Large Language Models for Rhythmic Classification of Free Verse Poetry

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Introduction

This work revisits the Rhythmicalizer project's approach to classify German free-verse Poetry into prosodic categories using deep learning (Baumann et al., 2018). The rise of Large Language Models (LLMs) and foundation models pre-trained on vast amounts of text and speech begs the question whether these are more appropriate for poetic tasks than the original project's model architecture. This study evaluates LLM and foundation model performance on the original corpus and compares them to the original results.

Two LLM variants are considered: decoder-only models (GPT-style LLMs), and encoder-only models (BERT; Devlin, 2019). Decoders are trained to generate text by repeatedly predicting the next token and are widely used for chatbots. We describe below how they are used for classification. Encoders in contrast produce contextualized embeddings that can be fed to a classification layer. Notably, we extend this approach to include the spoken form of the poem, which is impossible in a text-based decoder-only approach. For this, we extract features from the spoken audio using HuBERT (Hsu et al., 2021) and integrate these into a multimodal hierarchical architecture (Yang et al., 2016).

The data set is inherited by Rhythmicalizer and was obtained from the website *lyrikline* (Haus für Poesie, 2025). It consists of 2393 poems, most of them having corresponding text and audio files. Only 175 samples have a class la-

bel manually annotated by a philological expert. Figure 1 shows a sample from the data set from the *lettristic decomposition* class.

```

s c h t z n g r m m
  t - t - t - t
  t - t - t - t
g r r r m m m m m
  t - t - t - t
s ----- c ----- h
  t z n g r m m
  t z n g r m m
  t z n g r m m
g r r r m m m m m
[ . . . ]

```

Excerpt of the poem "schtzngrmm" by Ernst Jandl included in the data set.

Text-Audio Alignment

Like the previous work, the multimodal approach leverages text-audio alignments, which have been manually created for the original corpus. Additionally to updating the classification, we test the quality of automatic forced alignments via multilingual Wav2Vec2 (Pratap et al., 2024). Automatic timestamps were compared to manual timestamps and later used to re-train the classification model.

Decoder-based Classification

Conventional LLMs are optimized to generate from a prompt (or more generally: to produce likely continuations for some initial text). To use such a conventional decoder-only LLM for classification, we restrict the output probability distribution to an allowed set of class names. We use zero- and few-shot prompts that include descriptions of the prosodic classes to be predicted (with examples). Note that classifications are based on text alone as it is presently not possible to include speech with the models used (Llama 3.2:70b; Grattafiori, 2024).

Multimodal Encoder-based Classification

The multimodal classification model, including audio pre-processing.

In contrast to the decoder-only classifier, like Rhythmicizer, the encoder-based classification leverages both the text and audio recording of the poem. Unlike the original project, which encoded modalities with GRU-encoders, we use foundation models as modality encoders. Text is encoded by BERT base and audio by HuBERT base (using mean aggregation over all token embeddings). Figure 2 shows the architecture of the model including modality encoding and hierarchical feature extraction.

Experiments and Results

The main challenge for deep-learning experiments with the available corpus is its small size. For our *encoder-based model*, we therefore performed 25-fold cross-validation on the 175 labeled samples, which still leaves the model undertrained and far from optimal. The *decoder-LLM-based* approach does not require training. However, we found it to not yield meaningful results which we attribute to the difficult genre and the lack of speech processing. The updated multimodal classification model achieved a weighted F1-score comparable to the original Rhythmicizer but without fundamental improvements. Figure 3 compares the results.

Comparison of results.

Model	F1-Score
Original Architecture (Baumann et al., 2018)	0.73
Encoder-based – automated alignment	0.71
Encoder-based – manual alignment	0.70
Decoder-based – Zero-Shot	0.30
Decoder-based – Few-Shot	0.26

The *text-audio alignment* worked reliably across most rhythm classes, with weaknesses for poems not composed of full words. Still, replacing manual with automatic alignment annotations in the classification pipeline did not degrade classification performance. As a result, we can produce multi-modal classifications for the full corpus of several thousand poems. This greatly expands the toolbox for rapid analysis and exploration of spoken poetry, as it highlights the potential for fully automating the classification pipeline.

Discussion and Conclusion

Our multi-modal classifier works similarly well to the original Rhythmicizer. Text-only classification with an LLM remains insufficient for the task, which implies that current chatbots have a limited out-of-the-box understanding of prosodic patterns in post-modern poetry. We also found that automatic text-speech alignments can easily replace the originally required manual alignments for our model.

On this ground, we classified the full Lyrikline corpus (>2000 poems) and selected the (up to) 5 poems for which the classifier was most confident. We find that the original annotator of the Rhythmicizer corpus finds the classifications to be largely correct, except for syllabic decompositions and gestic rhythm. We believe our fully automated process can be a great tool to further analyze and understand post-modern poetic prosodies.

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